

Analysing Cooperative Human-Robot System as an Optimization Problem

Roy Someshwar & Yoav Kerner

*Dept. of Industrial Engineering and Management,
Ben-Gurion University of Negev, Beersheba, Israel 84105; e-mail: {royso, kerneryo}@bgu.ac.il*

An analytical model is presented as a possible methodology to analyse Human-Robot (H-R) cooperative systems that can collaborate as peers or co-workers in a shared work-, time-space for a common time-critical task [1] [2]. The joint-efficiency of the H-R system as a whole in a time-critical task is developed as an optimization problem. For this, an objective function is derived that accommodates all the operational and temporal costs of the system for a successful and fluent handover [3]. The performance of the system is then measured in terms of the fluency of the system or the successes of the coordination [4]. This is evaluated by solving the objective function for a solution that minimizes (or maximizes, if that is the goal) the overall cost of the system.

For a typical H-R cooperative system used in our analysis, there are two decision variables and three influencing parameters. The decision variables are t and A , the time when the human and robot is scheduled to arrive at the point of handover respectively. The parameters are C_R , the cost for an unproductive handover of the robot, C_H , the human waiting cost per time unit and the function $F_Y(\cdot)$, the distribution of the human delay (while the random human delay is denoted by Y). For a case of uniform delay, i.e. $F_Y(y) = y$, the total cost of the H-R system is,

$$C_h \frac{A - At + t^2}{2} + C_r \left(\left\lceil \frac{1+t}{A} \right\rceil \left(1+t - \frac{1}{2} \left(\left\lceil \frac{1+t}{A} \right\rceil - 1 \right) \right) - t \right)$$

and the system behaviour is shown below.

Figure 1. In the case of uniform delay (a) The graph shows the optimal value of A as a function of C_h (b) The graph shows the optimal cost of the system as a function of C_h [2]

References:

- [1] Hoffman, G., & Breazeal, C. (2007). Cost-based anticipatory action selection for human-robot fluency. *IEEE transactions on robotics*, 23(5), 952-961.
- [2] Someshwar, R., Meyer, J., & Edan, Y. (2012). Models and methods for HR synchronization. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 45(6), 829-834.
- [3] Someshwar, R., & Kerner, Y. (2013). Optimization of Waiting Time in HR Coordination. In *IEEE International Conference on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC)*.
- [4] Someshwar, R., Meyer, J., & Edan, Y. (2012). A timing control model for HR synchronization. *IFAC Proceedings Volumes*, 45(22), 698-703.